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Analyzing The Impact of Employee Engagement on Perceived Employee Performance: Role of Gender as a Moderating Variable. An Empirical Research on The Microfinance Industry in Egypt

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Abstract

Purpose – The present study examines the role of gender in the relationship between employee engagement and perceived employee performance within the microfinance industry in Egypt.

Design/ methodology/ approach – The present study population embraces all employees and managers in the 10 biggest microfinance companies in Egypt. The financial regulatory authority published the key players in the microfinance sector in Egypt. Participants were 340. Self-administered questionnaires were used to collect the data. The primary data was collected and analyzed using a popular component-based model called partial least squares (PLS).

Findings- The findings clearly reveal that all explanatory employee engagement has a significant impact on perceived employee performance (in-role performance and extra-role performance). Moreover, the statistical analysis showed that neither the coefficient of gender (moderating variable) on the relationship between employee engagement and perceived employee performance (in-role performance and extra-role performance) within the Egyptian microfinance industry.

Originality/value: The study contributes to the limited empirical scholarly research, adding to a deeper understanding of the impact of employee engagement on perceived employee performance. and what is the role of gender as a moderating variable in the Egyptian microfinance industry?

Keywords: Microfinance Industry in Egypt, Employee Engagement, Perceived Employee Performance, Gender.

1. Introduction

Himawaty, R. (2022) asserts that the significance of employee performance as a catalyst for attaining organizational objectives relates to an employee's competency in terms of what he or she can accomplish at work. a company has the ability to evaluate whatever behavior an employee exhibits while on the job, meaning that an individual's performance is evaluated based on the assignments or work that they are assigned. Additionally, Paais, M., & Pattiruhu, J. R. (2020) notes that a variety of circumstances can affect an employee's performance; in this instance, specific factors may be the driving force behind an employee's success.

In Egypt, microfinance underwent a significant transformation in the late 1980s. United States Agency for International Development (USAID) in Egypt launched a program in 1988 aimed at bringing about such improvements (El Hadidi, H. H. 2018). Despite, the significant impact of Egyptian microfinance which was highlighted by several studies, the majority of these studies were conducted within the scope of the impact of small begging on the Egyptian economy, as well as on the empowerment of women in Egypt like (El Hadidi, H. H. 2018; El Hadidi, H. 2020; Rashem, M. H., & Abdullah, Y. A. 2018; Nisser, A. H. I., & Ayedh et al, 2020).

On another hand numerous researchers have highlighted the many advantages of employee engagement. These advantages include competitive advantage as well as higher profitability and revenue growth. Due to their roles in improving individual and organizational performance, human resources management practitioners are needed to support the creation of initiatives aimed at promoting employee engagement if they are to fully realize the benefits of having a more engaged workforce (Jawahar, V. 2019).

There are two reasons why this research is relevant. The caliber of interactions between staff members and clients, as well as between employees, is a major factor in the success of microfinance companies. The majority of customers view frontline staff as their one and only point of contact with microfinance institutions. Frontline staff members are there throughout the entire credit process, serving as marketers and credit analysts in addition to approving and overseeing loans. This indicates that in the microfinance industry, staff are the most significant "factor of production". If they fail, the microfinance also fails with them especially for group-based lending (Kanyurhi et al,2016). Secondly, the Egyptian microfinance plays an important role in the socioeconomic development of poor and low-income people (El Hadidi, H. 2020).

This paper purports to test the effect of employee engagement on perceived employee performance within the microfinance industry in Egypt. This research contribution to the existing literature is twofold. First, it analyzes the relationship between employee engagement and perceived employee performance. Although employees play a central role in such organizations, their engagement has been less analyzed. Second, little is known about engagement dimensions in that particular sector. To develop hypotheses, the researchers begin with discussions about the theoretical framework. Thereafter, the researchers provide an analysis of the data collection and processing procedures. The results are presented and discussed in the third and fourth sections, respectively. In conclusion, the researchers conclude and discuss some limitations, implications, and future research perspectives.

2. Literature Review and Conceptual Model

2.1: Employee Engagement

According to Jawahar, V. (2019) The concept of employee engagement originated with research conducted by Kahn (1990), who established the ideas of personal engagement and disengagement. Engagement is the compliance of management and non-management employees with an organization regarding the organization's vision, mission and goals in their work processes (Vorina et al., 2017). According to Kreitner & Kinicki (2013), Employee Engagement is the level to which an employee immerses himself in the work he is doing. Another expression explains that Employee Engagement is also an emotional level in the organization which means that employees really care about their careers and the organization (Joushan, 2015).

Thus, employees with a high level of work involvement identify strongly and really care about the type of work they do (Himawaty, R. 2022). Vorina et al., (2017) explained that an employee's engagement can be measured by how much an employee contributes to the organization, an employee's dedication, strong will and employee pride in the organization. Seeing this, the indicators of employee engagement are (1) Dedication, (2) Vigor and (3) Absorption.

Himawaty, R. (2022) revealed that Employee Engagement is the degree to which a person identifies with a job, actively participates in it, and considers performance important for self-esteem. This form of self-esteem does not just extend to physical existence but also intellectual existence through obligations to achieve organizational goals (Vorina et al., 2017). So that employees who already have engagement will experience a high level of connectivity to their duties, which means that Employee Engagement is important exists, because good behavior from employees will influence a person's performance (Himawaty, R. 2022).

2.2: Employee Performance

According to Wang, C. H., & Chen, H. T, (2020), employee performance refers to the conduct and output of an individual within an organization in order to satisfy the requirements, policies, or official positions of the organization. Briefly stated, an individual exercising self-control's organizational goal-

related activities is referred to as performing their job, all activities done to accomplish organizational goals constitute job performance, and they also suggested that it is possible to quantify the contributions that these behaviors make.

According to Ridwan et al, (2020) Both in-role and extra-role performance can be used to define an employee's performance. When an employee performs in accordance with their job description, they are fulfilling their formal tasks, obligations, and responsibilities. This is known as in-role performance. While extra-role performance is the term for actions that are necessary for an organization to function well but are optional, such as being polite, lending a hand to others, and maintaining positive relationships with superiors and coworkers (Rubel, M. R. B., & Kee, D. M. H, 2013).

2.3: Relationship between Employee Engagement and Employee Performance

According to additional study, employees are more likely to perform well at work if they believe that their employers appreciate their contributions and are concerned about their welfare (Rubel & Kee, 2013). In this article, the researchers propose that employee engagement has an impact on in-role and extra- role performance because engaged employees take satisfaction in maintaining their connections with the company for an extended period of time. Additionally, studies assert that by keeping their skills, a firm can improve its competitive edge and boost performance through the engagement of its employees because they have the power to actually achieve the organization's goals, employees are therefore seen as the most important resource within the company (Allen et al, 2008).

In role performance is closely linked to individual duties and productivity as a result of each employee's engagement with the company. Conversely, extra-role performance results from an employee's engagement with the company beyond what is specifically included in their job description (Rubel, M. R. B., & Kee, D. M. H, 2013). Engaged employees do personal initiatives that either meet or surpass company goals (Zayed, A., Farghly, R. 2023).

According to job engagement theory, job engagement explicitly increases task performance by giving workers the drive to do well at work because they participate in activities that directly affect their task performance ratings, connect emotionally to their work, and concentrate more intently on completing their assigned jobs for longer periods of time, engaged employees perform better on tasks (Ozyilmaz, A. 2020). which allows us to define our hypotheses as follows:

H1: Employee engagement has a significant impact on in-role performance.

H2: Employee engagement has a significant impact on extra-role performance.

On another hand Kong, Y. (2009) refer that male and female employees of the organization engage in their jobs differently, particularly when it comes to the aspect of dedication. The jobs held by women are more valuable than those held by men because men tend to be more vigorous than women, it makes sense that male employees score higher than female employees on the vigor and absorption dimensions. Generally speaking, due to having a shorter time at work, male employees feel refreshed when they work, and this will strengthen their engagement in working out different tasks and duties.

It has long been believed that men and women differ in their attitudes and behaviors. These disparities have recently been linked to the socialization process, which has an impact on career prospects, familial dynamics, and cultural expectations for men and women. Women should therefore be expected to respond to their jobs in a different way than do males (Côté, K, et al, 2021). In response the researchers suggest that:

H3. Employee engagement affects in-role performance, with gender as a moderating variable.

H4. Employee engagement affects extra-role performance, with gender as a moderating variable.

**Fig. 1 Conceptual Model
Develop By Researchers**

3. Research Objectives

The researchers sought to test whether employee engagement had an effect on perceived employee performance. The sup objectives of the research are essentially:

Objective One: To determine whether there is a relationship between employee engagement and in role performance within microfinance industry in Egypt.

Objective Two: To explore what is the relationship between employee engagement and extra role performance within microfinance industry in Egypt.

Objective Three: To investigate what is the role of gender in the relationship between employee engagement and employee's performance within microfinance industry in Egypt.

4. Research Methodology

Study Design: A quantitative approach was applied to achieve the study objectives.

Population and Sample The current study selected 354 employees randomly from five companies within the microfinance industry in Egypt to fill out the questionnaires. 340 questionnaires were recovered, reaching a response rate of 97%.

Sample profile the sample descriptive profile displayed in table (1) shows that most of the sample respondents (65%) were females while male respondents were (35%). The majority of the respondents were from 25 to less than 35 years old, 55%. A total of 126 respondents (70%) were employees, and 103 respondents (30%) were managers.

Table (1) Response Description

	Sample Description	Number	%
Gender	Male	118	35%
	Female	222	65%
Age	Under 25 years old	40	12%
	From 25 to less than 35	186	55%
	From 35 to less than 45	94	28%
	From 45 to less than 55	16	4%
	55 years and over	4	1%
Career Level	Employee	237	70%
	Manager	103	30%

The scope of this study was the impact of employee engagement on perceived employee performance. Gender as a Moderating Variable within the Microfinance Industry in Egypt. Growing institutional support is responsible for the microfinance industry's recent expansion in Egypt. The first microfinance law was passed in 2014, which aided in the entry of new companies providing commercial microlending into the market. The Central Bank of Egypt (CBE) announced in August 2017 the launch of a microfinance project aimed at financing 30 billion Egyptian pounds to recipients, who will then provide subsidized funding to a number of microfinance enterprises. This is in line with the CBE's funding initiative, which mandates that small and medium enterprises be given access to 20% of banks' portfolios. The CBE asserts that this program will result in increased employment, financial inclusion, and economic growth due to the scale of the informal sector.

The data used in this study were primary and secondary data. Primary data is data obtained directly from the source, taken and recorded first. In this study, the primary data were respondent's answers to questionnaires related to the research variables. The primary data was obtained using the direct survey method or questionnaire distribution.

Measurement Tools: The researchers utilized a five-point Likert scale with responses ranging from strongly disagree (1) to strongly agree (5). The questionnaire was created based on validated scales. Employee engagement within the department is assessed by adopting Schaufeli, W. B., & Bakker, A. B. (2003) three factors included (vigor, dedication, and absorption). While employee performance is assessed by Lynch et al, (1999), two factors included: (In-role performance and Extra-role performance. The established translation-back-translation procedures of Brislin (1970) were followed to prepare the scales, which were originally designed and used in English, for use in Arabic.

5. Data Analysis

5.1; Model Evaluation

It's critical that researchers pay attention to both external and internal validity. Internal validity determines if mistakes or other plausible reasons exist to explain the results, whereas external validity evaluates the ability to extrapolate results from a specific sample to a larger population (Punch, 2005). The value or point of loading factor in Table 2 from all variables was above 0.50 so that this had already fulfilled its validity.

Table (2) Outer Loading

Factors	Employee Engagement	In-role performance	Extra-role performance
Ab1	0.651		
Ab2	0.548		
Ab3	0.641		
Ab4	0.635		
Ab5	0.694		
Ab6	0.503		
De1	0.695		
De2	0.734		
De3	0.756		
De4	0.748		
De5	0.727		
EXRP2		0.821	
EXRP3		0.823	
EXRP4		0.872	
EXRP5		0.816	
EXRP7		0.661	
InRP1			0.660
InRP2			0.720
InRP3			0.647
InRP4			0.737

InRP5			0.791
InRP6			0.666
InRP7			0.747
InRP8			0.763
InRP9			0.639
Vi2	0.760		
Vi3	0.656		
Vi4	0.623		
Vi5	0.615		
Vi6	0.592		
Vi1	0.713		

We had to assess the discriminant validity and composite reliability of the data in an attempt to gauge its dependability. Cross loading demonstrated discriminant validity. When comparing the correlation value between an indicator and another, the correlation value between the indicator and its construct ought to be higher. Table 3 displayed the discriminant validity's worth in the interim. The Fornel-Lacker criterion (Hair, Sarstedt, Ringle, & Mena, 2012) were applied to the PLS results, and it was discovered that each construct's AVE was greater than its correlation value. This implied that every construct in a single model that had undergone estimation satisfied the requirements for discriminant validity.

Table 3 Discriminant Validity

	Employee Engagement	In-role performance	Extra-role performance
Employee Engagement	0.668		
In-role performance	0.614	0.802	
Extra-role performance	0.604	0.585	0.710

Furthermore, Cronbach alpha from the indicator's unit measurement construct might also be used to gauge the construct dependability. When the construct's Cronbach alpha value was higher than 0.70, it indicated that the construct had greater dependability.

Pearson's bivariate correlations between study variables are reported in Table 4. presents the findings of the Pearson correlation matrix (Pearson's r) between the study variables. As shown in Table 4 below, employee engagement positively and significantly associated with in-role performance (.580**), and with extra-role performance (.530**).

Table 4 Means, SD and intercorrelations between the study variables

	M	SD	Employee Engagement	In-role performance	Extra-role performance
Employee Engagement	4.25	.540	1		
In-role performance	4.55	.441	.580**	1	
Extra-role performance	4.42	.549	.530**	.585**	1

* $p < .05$.

** $p < .01$.

5.2; Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis testing was conducted based on the path coefficient method. Based on Table 4 on path coefficients, the impact between variables could be analyzed as follows: The impact of employee engagement on in-role performance was significant and positive, with its coefficient value of 0.604 and a P-value of 0.000. While employee engagement on extra-role performance was 0.614 and the P-value was 0.000.

Third, employee engagement affects in-role performance, with gender as a moderating variable. It was found that the study result showed that the P-value was 0.661. This meant that its hypothesis was rejected

because, in fact, gender did not strengthen the effect of employee engagement on in-role performance. Finally, H4 stated that gender reinforces the influence employee engagement on extra-role performance. Table 4 showed that t-values is 0.736 (<1.64) and p-value is 0.059 (>0.05). Therefore, H4 was not accepted.

Table5 Hypothesis-testing

	Original Sample (O)	T statistics	P-Value	Hypothesis
Employee Engagement > In-Role Performance	0.604	7.203	0.000	Accepted
Employee Engagement > Extra-Role Performance	0.614	8.394	0.000	Accepted
Employee Engagement *Gender> In-Role Performance	-0.039	0.410	0.661	Rejected
Employee Engagement * Gender> Extra-Role Performance	0.207	0.736	0.059	Rejected

6. Discussion

The interrelation between employee engagement and perceived employee performance has been theoretically and empirically articulated. Notwithstanding, the existing studies have not yet provided a profound understanding of the effect of the impact of employee engagement on perceived employee performance in the Egyptian microfinance industry and the role of gender in this relationship.

And answering two study questions focused on the exploration of the relationship between employee engagement, perceived employee performance, and gender differences. With respect to the first question (i.e., what's the relationship between employee engagement and in-role performance and extra role performance within the microfinance industry in Egypt), we observed that employee engagement is positively and significantly associated with in-role performance and extra role performance (.580**), (.530**) respectively. In addition, in-role and extra-role performance impacted by employee engagement was positive, which means microfinance sector companies in Egypt should enhance employee participation in decisions related to their jobs, such as their KPIs. And also involve them in strategic decisions, such as the company's goals. These findings are in line with the previous literature (Rubel, M. R. B., & Kee, D. M. H, 2013; Rubel & Kee, 2013; Allen et al, 2008).

On the other hand, concerning the second study question (i.e., is gender moderating in the relationship between employee engagement and perceived employee performance). The study aimed to explore the presence of gender differences in study variables, and we observed no gender differences between males and females in the relationship between employee engagement and perceived employee performance. This result differs from previous studies, most previous studies have proven that employee engagement differs between men and women (Kong, Y. 2009; Côté, K, et al,2021).

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